

ADMINISTRATIVE PERFORMANCE AND INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP OF SCHOOL HEADS IN PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS

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Administrative Performance and Instructional Leadership of School Heads in Public Elementary Schools

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Abstract

The study sought to determine the influence of school heads' administrative performance and instructional leadership practices to teachers' teaching performance of public elementary schools. Descriptive-correlational research method was utilized and the study included statistical tools such as mean, standard deviation, frequency count, and percentages to examine the degree of administrative performance and instructional leadership practices of school heads, as well as the teaching performance of teachers. The Pearson-Product Moment Correlation was used to determine the noteworthy association between the instructional leadership practices of school heads and the administrative performance of teachers as well as the administrative performance of the school heads and teachers' level of teaching performance. Findings revealed that school heads to the "very high extent" performed their administrative performance of planning, organizing, directing, and to the "high extent" performed its controlling function. The also practiced to the "very high extent" their instructional leadership in terms of administration and supervision of instructional program, human resource development program, and students' services and development program. Further, it was revealed that majority 91% of the teachers had an "outstanding" teaching performance. However, it was found out that school heads' administrative performance and instructional leadership had negligible correlation to teachers' level of teaching performance. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. As a summary, it was recommended that school heads must continue to provide in-service trainings in the areas of classroom management, technology and education as well as on educational innovation to sustain their outstanding teaching performance.

Keywords: *administrative performance, instructional leadership, students' services, human resource development*

Introduction

Global leaders are challenged to respond proactively to the issues and concerns that adversely affect the employees' work performance effectiveness and productivity in their workplace in both private and public business and corporate organizations.

The study's framework is constrained by the legal and philosophical foundations of section 4 of rule 3 (Duties and Obligations of the School Heads) of the Education Act of 1982, which states that: "the school head or school principals shall perform their duties to the school by discharging their responsibilities in accordance with the philosophy, goals, and objectives of the school and develop as well as maintain a healthy school atmosphere conducive to harmonious and progressive school-personnel relationships, and to the promotion and preservation of academic freedom and effective teaching-learning, assume and maintain professionalism in the exercise of their leadership in their work and in their dealings with students, teachers, academic non-teaching personnel, administrative staff, and parents or guardians".

School heads perform numerous functions and routinely administrative duties including class observations, teachers' clinical supervision, conducting the school-based learning action cell or in-house trainings for teachers, attending parental and teachers' concerns, conducting meetings, and forging community and school relations.

The principles of Republic Act (RA) 9155, also referred to as the "Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001," serve as the foundation for the administrative and instructional leadership of school heads in public secondary schools. This act highlights the crucial role that school heads play in influencing the productive and successful performance of classroom teachers.

The intricacies in the modern world due to the advancement of science and technology have brought many changes not only in work place but also in the interpersonal and working relationships of teachers in school organization particularly in public secondary schools.

Effective and innovative management of instructional activities in public secondary school require school heads who can truly inspire teachers to stimulate learners to learn and initiate change and innovations to make learning more interesting, rewarding, and meaningful.

It is the challenge of the school heads in the public school to produce learners who will soon take the leadership rule in the future and to transform more productive human organizations, possess creativity and innovativeness, and above all the intelligence to propel the country's socio-economic and political change and development. However, all of these need the effective management of instructional activities and transformational leadership of the school heads.

Transformational school heads are those who can inspire and motivate teachers to continuously aspire for quality instruction and a leader who can recognize visible quality commitment from all their subordinates.

As Aguilar (2018) puts it, the most effective way of managing human capital in the organization is to help provide opportunities for professional enhancement, equip individuals with skills, facilitate adoption of technological innovations, and create more productive

teams and enable better communication throughout the organization.

One of the best attributes of the school heads according to Jaramillo (2017) is their ability to coach, manage, and develop more effective and productive team members in the school organization to achieve the desired educational objectives.

Consequently, administrative efficacy requires school heads to successfully communicate and relate well with teachers and academic support personnel; professionally handle personal and work-related problems; introduce change; and inspire others to become virtuous team players.

School heads as instructional leaders in public secondary schools necessitate to possess the earlier-stated characteristics because they are tasked and responsible to take a dynamic role in translating policies, plans and programs of the academic institutions into work operations for the attainment of school's educational thrusts.

Instructional effectiveness is dependent on how school heads of each academic unit of the public school their administrative functions of planning, organizing, directing, staffing, coordinating, reporting, budgeting, decision making, and human resource development (Plunkett, 2005).

Researches revealed that performance of administrative functions is influenced by the socio-demographic factors which include age, gender, educational attainment, academic ranks, and number of years in the academic institutions of the school heads. Greaves (2005) has espoused that socio-demographic characteristics and a thorough understanding or knowledge on the administrative functions have the greatest influence to the school heads' administrative performance and instructional leadership.

However, issues on instructional leadership particularly in the areas of teachers' teaching effectiveness, trainings and development, promotion, students' misbehavior, and ancillary functions are some of the issues that may influence teachers' discouragement and work dissatisfaction which, in effect, stemmed to the subsequent sickness and even death of teachers is predominant.

It is in the light of the aforecited circumstances, that the purpose of the study, which is to identify the administrative and instructional leadership of school heads in public secondary schools who are responsible for delivering an equally accessible and high-quality public education, is what drives the researcher.

Research Questions

The purpose of the study was to ascertain how school heads' instructional leadership and administrative performance affected the public elementary school teachers' ability to teach. Specifically, the study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of school heads' administrative performance in terms of:
 - 1.1. planning;
 - 1.2. organizing;
 - 1.3. directing; and
 - 1.4. controlling?
2. What is the extent of school heads' instructional leadership in terms of:
 - 2.1. administration and supervision of instructional activities and programs;
 - 2.2. human resource development program; and
 - 2.3. students' services and development program?
3. What is the level of teachers' teaching performance in terms of the following categories:
 - 3.1. outstanding;
 - 3.2. very satisfactory;
 - 3.3. satisfactory; and
 - 3.4. unsatisfactory?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' level of teaching performance and the schools heads' administrative performance?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' teaching performance and school heads' instructional leadership?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive correlational- research design. Descriptive research according to Calderon, et al (2012) is a fact-finding inquiry or investigation. It is employed to develop a thorough knowledge of the primary causes of the given situations.

In addition, descriptive design as an inquiry uses an in-depth analysis of the problem which data collection methods include, but not limited to an interview and observation.

Subsequently, descriptive research design was used to quantify the problem by way of generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into usable statistics. This method measures variables through the use of quantifiable or finite data and the analysis was

based on generated information from statistical tools. This method was also used in an inquiry with larger population.

Respondents

The respondents of the study are the public elementary school heads and teachers in East 2 District, Division of Gingoog City.. There were eight (8) public elementary schools which used in this study. There were eight (8) school heads in East 2 as the sample respondents and ten (10) teachers each school who were used to evaluate their school head through survey-questionnaire. The total teacher -respondents in schools were eighty (80).

The researcher is using scientific random sampling ,specifically, unrestricted random sampling where the teacher-respondents are chosen thru lottery or table random numbers to get the sample teacher- respondent. As to the number of teacher -respondents which is only ten(10) each schools, are purposively decided for the convenient accessibility of the researcher.

<i>Schools</i>	<i>School Head</i>	<i>Teachers</i>
Mimbalagon Integrated School	1	10
Tinabalan Elementary School	1	10
Mimbunga Elementary School	1	10
Maribucan Elementary School	1	10
Minsapinit Elementary School	1	10
Bagubad Elementary School	1	10
Anakan Central School	1	10
Punong Elementary School	1	10
Total	8	80

Instrument

The study utilized the survey questionnaire adapted from Dramayo (2014) on the administrative practices and instructional leadership effectiveness of school heads. The survey questionnaire on administrative performance of school heads was composed of two parts. Part I is the administrative functions along the areas of planning, organizing, directing, and controlling functions of the school heads in Public Elementary Schools.

Subsequently, Part II is on the dimensions which measure instructional leadership effectiveness of the school heads along the three dimensions, namely; administration and supervision of instructional activities; human resource development program; and students' services and development program.

Procedure

The study on the administrative performance and instructional leadership of school heads for the 2022–2023 school year was approved by the Gingoog City Division Schools Division Superintendent. After the approval, the researcher administered the research instrument to the Elementary Schools of East 2 District. The research instruments retrieved immediately after the respondents provided the data needed. Results were recorded, tallied, tabulated, and analyzed using appropriate statistical treatment.

Data Analysis

The following statistical techniques are utilized in the study:

Problem 1. To determine the extent of school heads' administrative performance, mean values and standard deviations was used.

Problem 2. To determine the extent of school heads' instructional leadership, mean values and standard deviations was used.

Problem 3. To ascertain the significant relationship between the school heads' administrative performance and respondents' profile, Pearson-Product Moment Correlation will be utilized.

Problem 4. To ascertain the significant relationship between the school heads' instructional leadership Spearman - Rho Correlation was used.

Results and Discussion

This section includes the findings from the study on the instructional leadership and administrative performance of school heads in public primary schools, as well as its presentation, analysis, and interpretation. Based on the given problem, data analysis and interpretation are conducted.

Problem 1. What is the Extent of School Heads' Administrative Performance in terms of; Planning, Organizing, Directing, and Controlling?

School's performance is attributed to school heads' ability to execute its administrative and management functions such as planning, organizing, directing, and organizing of all its human and material resources to better accomplish the school's thrusts and goals and

help achieves the educational objectives of developing learners' learning competencies.

Table 1.1 shows the mean distribution of the extent of school heads' administrative performance in terms of planning function.

Table 1.1. *Mean Distribution of School Heads' Administrative Performance in terms of Planning*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Set goals and objectives, workable plans and programs of activities for the school.	4.72	.449	Very High Extent
2. Determines the resources needed within the school.	4.60	.492	Very High Extent
3. Identifies the needs and problems of the school and find ways and means of solving it.	4.58	.520	Very High Extent
Overall Mean	4.63	.487	Very High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High Extent/3.41-4.20 High Extent/2.61-3.40 Moderate Extent/1.81-2.60 Less/low Extent/1.00-1.80 No Extent

Table 1.1 displays the mean distribution of school heads' administrative performance in terms of planning. Overall, the respondents rated the school head's administrative performance in terms of planning as "Very High Extent" with a mean of 4.63 (SD=.487). This result indicates that the school heads always set goals and objectives and workable plans and determines resources needed to achieve school's goals as well as efficiently and effectively achieve schools' objectives through an effective and careful planning activities.

The indicator "set goals and objectives, workable plans and programs of activities for the school" obtained the highest mean value of 4.72 (SD=.449) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" which implies that planning as the primary function of the school heads was always practiced and was extremely implemented by the school heads. It can also be deduced that planning was highly practiced by the school heads to provide achieve goals and objectives of the school organization and at the same time to ensure that strategies to achieve the goals are best considered.

Saldana (2021) emphasized that school heads created plan of action for providing quality education to students. The planning function involves setting goals and objectives for the educational system as well as determining how to achieve those goals best. Additionally, it was also underscored that planning also involves making decisions about what resources are needed in order to provide the best possible education for all students.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.58 (SD=.520) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" in the indicator "identifies the needs and problems of the school and find ways and means of solving it". The result indicates that the school heads' planning function was extremely implemented especially in the identification and determination of the different issues and challenges of the school as well as the strategies of addressing of such were exceptionally observed. Thus, it is imperative that the school heads to properly plan the activities and development programs of the school in order to ensure effective implementation of the same and achieve school's goals and objectives.

Parveen, et al (2021) averred that school heads' planning function plays an important role in school heads' performance in leading the school organization and encouraging teachers to participate in addressing and resolving issues and challenges and other school-related concerns.

Table 1.2. *Mean Distribution of School Heads' Administrative Performance in terms of Organizing*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Identifies the work activities to be done to accomplish the objectives.	4.71	.455	Very High Extent
2. Assigns the work to individual teacher and delegate the appropriate authority.	4.63	.509	Very High Extent
3. Recommends promotion or merit increase to deserving teachers.	4.52	.550	Very High Extent
4. Sends teachers or recommends to seminars, conferences, meetings, and other in-service training to improve work and teaching performance.	4.80	.402	Very High Extent
Overall Mean	4.67	.479	Very High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High Extent/3.41-4.20 High Extent/2.61-3.40 Moderate Extent/1.81-2.60 Less/low Extent/1.00-1.80 No Extent

Table 1.2 shows the mean distribution of the administrative performance in terms of organizing for school heads. Overall, with a mean score of 4.67 (SD=.479), the respondents assessed the school heads' organizational role as being at "Very High Extent." This result indicates that the school heads extremely practiced organizing function in the school organization from the conduct of professional development training programs for teachers, recommends for promotion to assigning and delegating responsibilities and ancillary assignments to teachers. It can be inferred based on findings that school heads organize all the resources in order to achieve the schools' goals and objectives.

Bas, et al (2020) pointed out that organizing function of the school heads involves developing an organizational structure and allocating resources to ensure the accomplishments of school objectives. It was also emphasized that the school heads' organizing function involves allocating the human resources to work together to achieve specific goals. It also includes tasks alignment and division of labor among teachers to meet the school's ultimate purpose.

The indicator "sends teachers or recommends teachers to seminars, conferences, meetings, and other in-service trainings to improve work and teaching performance" obtained the highest mean value of 4.80 (SD=.402) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" which indicates that school heads always recommend teachers for professional development such as seminars, conferences, and other

in-service training programs to uplift teachers' teaching competence and effectiveness. Thus, it is imperative that the school heads will always practice effective organizing functions in order to help the school attain its desired objectives.

This finding was supported by Marzano (2021) who suggests that school heads' organizing function includes developing teachers through attendance to training programs in order to give them the opportunity for continuous professional development which help them learn new strategies and methods of teaching and assessment of learning.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.25 (SD= .550) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" in the indicator "recommends promotion or merit increase to deserving teachers" It can be deduced based on findings that school heads enormously provide opportunities to teachers for promotion and equal chance for professional advancement. Bredeson (2020) pointed out that principals consistently fulfilled most of their roles stated in PPSSH: personal and professional development; professional reflection; performance management; professional development of school personnel; leadership and development in individuals and teams; general welfare of human resources; and rewards and recognition, except for the professional networks strand.

It was also emphasized that both teacher and principal participants agree that principals serve as effective models for teachers, with a positive attitude about work, providing technical assistance and opportunities for teachers to assume relevant tasks, according recognition, developing soft skills of teachers, pursuing further study, and self-initiative as promotion requirements.

These findings suggest that a career advancement system should include three key competencies: functional, core behavioral, and professionalism and ethics. These should continuously and systematically address concerns of teachers about promotion and better meet organizational needs.

Table 1.3. Mean Distribution of School Heads' Administrative Performance in terms of Directing

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Made policies, rules, and regulations for the internal operation of the school.	4.62	.512	Very High Extent
2. Issues memoranda for the teachers to follow the desired courses of action.	4.50	.573	Very High Extent
Overall Mean	4.56	.543	Very High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High Extent/3.41-4.20 High Extent/2.61-3.40 Moderate Extent/1.81-2.60 Less/low Extent/1.00-1.80 No Extent

Table 1.3 displays the mean distribution of school heads' administrative performance in terms of directing. Overall, the respondents rated the directing as "Very High Extent" with a mean of 4.56 (SD=.543). This result indicates that school heads exceptionally exercise the directing function in the school organization. It can also be deduced based on finding that school heads made internal policies, rules and regulations for the internal operation of the school direct teachers through memoranda, notices and issuances for teachers' information and direction.

The indicator "made policies, rules and regulations for internal operation of the school" obtained the highest mean value of 4.62 (SD=.512) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" which implies that in school heads always provide notices to teachers especially during meetings and conferences as communication mechanisms in school organization as part of the directing functions of school heads. It is imperative for the school head to initiate and outline policies, rules and regulations as well as issuances or notices to keep teachers informed and direct activities within the organization.

This finding was supported by Cheng and Tsui (2020) who affirmed that school heads performed administrative function in terms of directing to ensure that communication, instruction, supervision of teachers is guaranteed and to warrant that teachers are working towards the accomplishments of the school's goals and objectives.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.50 (SD=.573 which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" in the indicator "issues memoranda for the teachers to follow the desired courses of action" It can be deduced based on findings that school heads issue notices and memo for information and announcements.

Parveen, et al (2021) purported that the most effective and efficient function of the school head is to direct performance of teachers through issuances of notice and memoranda to update and provide information to teachers of the activities of the school and to provide guidance and oversee the performance of teachers in order to achieve the predetermined goals. Additionally, it was emphasized that directing function of the school heads help create an appropriate work environment that facilitates efficient discharge of duties.

Table 1.4. Mean Distribution of School Heads' Administrative Performance in terms of Controlling

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Steers performance towards desired effective teaching results	3.91	1.715	High Extent
2. Prepares timetable for the accomplishment of the school or institution.	3.90	1.710	High Extent
3. Supervises teachers in school to see if all assigned tasks are done and accomplished.	3.95	1.728	High Extent
Overall Mean	3.92	1.718	High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High Extent/3.41-4.20 High Extent/2.61-3.40 Moderate Extent/1.81-2.60 Less/low Extent/1.00-1.80 No Extent

Table 1.4 shows the mean distribution of school heads' administrative performance in terms of organizing. Overall, the respondents rated the extent of the controlling function of the school heads as "High Extent" with a mean of 3.92 (SD=1.718). This result indicates

that the school heads exceedingly practiced controlling function in the school organization to ensure that activities in school are performed as planned. It can be deduced based on findings that controlling function also ensures that the school heads supervise properly the school's resources are being used and utilized effectively and efficiently for the achievement of the predetermined goals.

Bas, et al (2020) pointed out that controlling function of the school heads allow them to check teachers' work and assigned tasks are accomplished and performed well. Additionally, it was emphasized that controlling is the last management function which allow the school heads to compare between the actual teachers' performance and the planned performance so that corrective measures can be taken in case of any deviations or difference.

The indicator "supervises teachers in school to see if all assigned tasks are done and accomplished" obtained the highest mean value of 3.95 (SD=1.728) which is verbally described as "High Extent" which indicates that school heads most of the time control the activities in school. It can be deduced based on finding that the school heads closely supervise teachers if they are performing well in their teaching jobs and other ancillary work assignments.

This finding was supported by Marzano (2021) who suggests that school heads control through supervision of teachers' teaching and non-teaching related activities to ensure that they perform well and the assigned tasks are performed properly and teaching objectives are accomplished and achieved.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 3.90 (SD= 1.710) which is verbally described as "High Extent" in the indicator "prepares timetable for the accomplishments of the school or institution". It can be deduced based on findings that school heads immensely control the activities in accomplishing tasks through outlining timetable to ensure easy monitoring of teachers' work accomplishments.

Tirana (2021) averred that preparation of timetable matrix for easy monitoring of compliance and accomplishments of tasks is the best and most effective strategy of administrative proves of measuring performance and comparing the same with the standards. Additionally, the level of accomplishments of tasks assigned to teachers from the timetable serves as the basis for any corrective actions the school heads must implement to ensure effective and efficient running of the schools' activities.

Problem 2. What is the extent of school heads' instructional leadership in terms of; Administration and supervision of instructional activities and programs, Human Resource Development program, Students' services and development program

Table 2.1 presents the extent of school heads' instructional leadership in terms of administration and supervision of instructional activities and programs.

Table 2.1. *Mean Distribution of the Extent of School Heads' Instructional Leadership in terms of Administration and Supervision of Instructional Activities and Programs*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. Observes classes	4.82	.382	Very High Extent
2. Encourages teachers conduct researches to enhance teaching effectiveness.	4.58	.520	Very High Extent
3. Provides necessary academic counselling to teachers to enhance teaching effectiveness.	4.68	.559	Very High Extent
Overall Mean	4.69	.487	Very High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High Extent/3.41-4.20 High Extent/2.61-3.40 Moderate Extent/1.81-2.60 Less/low Extent/1.00-1.80 No Extent

Table 2.1 presents the mean distribution of the extent of school heads' instructional leadership in terms of administration and supervision of instructional activities and programs. Overall, the respondents rated the extent of the school heads' administration and supervision of instructional activities and programs as "Very High Extent" with a mean value of 4.69 (SD=.487). This result implies that the school heads exceedingly perform their functions in the areas of school and administrative leadership, coordination, personnel care, research, and public relations. School heads who performed their administration and supervision functions observe classes, encourage teachers conduct researches to improve teaching pedagogy and work performance, and provide needed counselling to improve teaching performance.

The indicator "observes classes" obtained the highest mean value of 4.82 (SD=.382) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" which indicates that school heads religiously and regularly observe classes in order to monitor teachers' teaching effectiveness and their basis for the provision of technical assistance to teachers.

Archibong (2022) suggests that class observation allows the school head to monitor teachers' teaching effectiveness and performance. Class observation is one of the administrative and supervisory approach for quality assurance and proactive means of ensuring quality in teaching.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.58 (SD= .520) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" in the indicator "encourages teachers conduct researches to enhance teaching effectiveness. It can be deduced based on findings that school heads always stimulate teachers to conduct researches in order to find best and most effective and efficient teaching strategies.

This finding was supported by Archibong (2022) who emphasized that the search for effective and efficient teaching methods is continuous, teachers are encouraged to conduct and write researches to find out the best strategies in improving teaching and enhancing

learners' learning performance.

Table 2.2 shows the instructional leadership of the school head in terms of human resource development program

Table 2.2. *Mean Distribution of the Extent of School Heads' Instructional Leadership in terms of Administration and Supervision of Human Resource Development Program*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Conducts needs assessment to teachers and academic support personnel.	4.56	.499	Very High Extent
2. Designs teachers and support staffs' development programs.	4.57	.497	Very High Extent
3. Encourages teachers to pursue graduate and post-graduate education.	4.81	.394	Very High Extent
4. Recommends or sends teachers to seminars, conferences, and trainings.	4.71	.482	Very High Extent
Overall Mean	4.66	.468	Very High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High Extent/3.41-4.20 High Extent/2.61-3.40 Moderate Extent/1.81-2.60 Less/low Extent/1.00-1.80 No Extent

Table 2.2 presents the mean distribution of the extent of school heads' instructional leadership in terms of human resource development program. Overall, the respondents rated the extent of the school heads' human resource development program as "Very High Extent" with a mean value of 4.66 (SD=.468). This result implies that the school heads extremely emphasized the development of human resources through teachers to training, seminars and conferences, graduate education, and the like.

The indicator "encourages teachers to pursue graduate and post-graduate education" obtained the highest mean value of 4.81 (SD=.394) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" which indicates that school heads always encouraged teachers to take their professional development through graduate and post-graduate education. It can be inferred based on findings that school heads emphasized the importance of professional development of teachers through advance education.

Afandi (2023) pointed out that graduate and post-graduate education allow teachers to deepen knowledge and acquire highly specialized expertise in a chosen field, or thinking of widening their career opportunities and increasing changes for career advancement. Teachers can help set your career path apart from others

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.56 (SD= .499) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" in the indicator "conducts need assessment to teachers and academic support personnel". It can be deduced based on findings that school heads always conduct assessments of teachers' needs and provide academic support to school personnel. Thus, it is imperative for the school heads to assess and evaluate the needs of teachers and other school personnel. Archibong (2022) asserted that school heads should always provide regular assessments on the needs of teachers and other school personnel in order to identify areas for improvement and personal development. It also helps teachers evaluate areas for improvement. It identifies gaps between the current conditions in a school and the desired conditions.

Table 2.3. *Mean Distribution of the Extent of School Heads' Instructional Leadership in terms of Administration and Supervision of Students' Services and Development*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.) Facilitates the improvement of media-resource center of the school.	4.58	.520	Very High Extent
2.) Encourages students' participation and collaboration in school and community actions.	4.77	.449	Very High Extent
3.) Facilitates in the provision of equipment for students' physical developments such as sports and athletics.	4.51	.503	Very High Extent
Overall Mean	4.62	.491	Very High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High Extent/3.41-4.20 High Extent/2.61-3.40 Moderate Extent/1.81-2.60 Less/low Extent/1.00-1.80 No Extent

Table 2.3 presents the mean distribution of the extent of school heads' instructional leadership in terms of students' services development program. Overall, the respondents rated the extent of the students' services development program as "Very High Extent" with a mean value of 4.62 (SD=.491). This result implies that the school heads strengthen the delivery of quality education by helping the school provides basic students' support services such as conducive learning environment and ensure learner's readiness through the timely mobilization and equitable distribution of sufficient resources, provision of technical support.

The indicator "encourages students' participation and collaboration in school and community actions" obtained the highest mean value of 4.77 (SD=.449) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" which implies that school heads ensure that students participate and collaborate in school and community actions. This is to develop students' social awareness, builds teamwork, communication, relationships, and a sense of belonging, all of which help students to develop socially and be successful in school.

Cockpim and Somprach (2021) suggest that school heads should encourage teachers to stimulate students to participate and collaborate in school activities and community involvement programs. This will help students develop socially and demonstrate importance of community involvement.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.51 (SD= .503) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" in the indicator "facilitates in the provision of equipment for students' physical developments such as sports and athletics". This finding indicates that part of the

schools' services to students is the provision of sports and athletics equipment to students. This is to stimulate development of sports and athletics.

Archibong (2022) avowed that one of the responsibilities of the school heads is to facilitate the release and provision of sports equipment and athletics implements to improve sports activities and development in school. It was also added that sports activities can help students to develop self-confidence and self-esteem.

Problem 3. What is the level of teachers' teaching performance in terms of the following categories; Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Unsatisfactory, and Poor?

Table 3. *Frequency Distribution of Teachers' Teaching Performance*

<i>Performance</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Outstanding	73	91%
Very Satisfactory	7	9%
Satisfactory	0	0%
Unsatisfactory	0	0%
Poor	0	0%

It can be asserted that out of 80 respondents, 73 (91%) had an "Outstanding" teaching performance while only 7 or 9% of the respondents had a "Very Satisfactory" teaching performance. This indicates that majority of the teachers performed tremendously and reasonably high due to the school head's ability to empower teachers and provide them with the most effective and efficient instructional leadership as well as positive administrative performance of the school heads.

It can also be asserted that the higher percentage of teachers' teaching performance was inspired by the school heads' ability to stimulate school resources such as the administration and supervision of instructional activities and programs, human resource development program, and students' services development program.

This finding was supported by Murphy and Hallinger (2020) who exemplified that school heads' administrative performance and instructional leadership contribute to teachers' teaching effectiveness.

Problem 4. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' level of teaching performance and the school heads' administrative performance?

Table 4. *Significant Relationship Between the Teachers' Level of Teaching Performance and the School Heads' Administrative Performance*

<i>School Heads' Administrative Performance</i>	<i>Teachers' Level of Teaching Performance</i>			
	<i>(rs)</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision on Ho1</i>
Planning	.078	.494	Denotes negligible correlation	Accepted
Organizing	.100	.379	Denotes negligible correlation	Accepted
Directing	.054	.64	Denotes negligible correlation	Accepted
Controlling	.131	.247	Denotes negligible correlation	Accepted

As depicted in table 4, school heads' administrative performance in terms of planning denotes negligible correlation to teachers' level of teaching performance as evident by the computed rs value of .078 which is lower than the p-value of .494. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. It can be deduced based on findings that teachers' teaching performance was not influenced by school heads' administrative performance in terms of planning. It can be inferred based on findings that there are other factors that influenced teachers' teaching performance other than the school heads' administrative performance in terms of planning.

Further, school heads' administrative performance in terms of organizing denotes negligible correlation to teachers' level of teaching performance as evident by the computed rs value of .100 which is lower than the p-value of .379. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted. It can be inferred based on findings that teachers' teaching performance was not influenced by school heads' administrative performance in terms of organizing. It can also be deduced that there are other variable that influence teachers' teaching performance other than the school heads' administrative performance in terms of organizing.

Subsequently, school heads' administrative performance in terms of directing denotes negligible correlation to teachers' level of teaching performance as evident by the computed rs value of .054 which is lower than the p-value of .64. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. It can be inferred based on findings that teachers' teaching performance was not influenced by school heads' administrative performance in terms of directing. It can also be deduced that there are other variable that influence teachers' teaching performance other than the school heads' administrative performance in terms of directing.

Successively, school heads' administrative performance in terms of controlling negligibly correlation to teachers' level of teaching performance as evident by the computed rs value of .131 which is lower than the p-value of .247. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. It can be argued understandably, that teachers' teaching performance was not influenced by the school heads' administrative

performance in terms of controlling. Teachers' teaching performance can be attributed to other factors not mentioned in this study.

These findings were in contrary to the findings of Bas, et al, Bredeson, Cheng and Tsui (2020) and Parveen, et al., Tirana, and Saldana (2021) who pointed out that teachers' teaching performance was influenced by school heads' administrative performance in terms of planning, organizing, directing, and controlling functions. It can be inferred plausibly and judiciously that teachers' teaching performance can be attributed to other factors and variables not included in the study such as teachers' teaching dedication and commitment to the teaching profession, trainings and seminars attended, and educational preparations for the teaching position.

Problem 5. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' teaching performance and the school heads' instructional leadership?

Table 5. Significant Relationship Between the Teachers' Level of Teaching Performance and the School Heads' Instructional Leadership

<i>School Heads' Instructional Leadership</i>	<i>Teachers' Level of Teaching Performance</i>			
	<i>(rs)</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision on Ho1</i>
Administration and Supervision	.101	.371	Denotes negligible correlation	Accepted
Human Resource Development Program	.062	.585	Denotes negligible correlation	Accepted
Students' Services and Development Program	.002	.986	Denotes negligible correlation	Accepted

Table 5 presents the interplay between the school heads' instructional leadership and teachers' level of teaching performance. The table depicts that school heads' instructional leadership in terms of administration and supervision of instructional program denotes negligible correlation to teachers' level of teaching performance as evident in the computed *rs* value of .101 which is lower than the *p*-value of .371. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. It can be argued that there is no significant relationship between the teachers' level of teaching performance and the school heads' instructional leadership practices in terms of administration and supervision of instructional activities and programs.

In addition, school heads' instructional leadership in terms of human resource development program denotes negligible correlation to teachers' level of teaching performance as evident in the computed *rs* value of .062 which is lower than the *p*-value of .585. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted. It can be deduced based on findings that human resource development program of the school heads as component of their instructional leadership does not influenced teachers' level of teaching performance and effectiveness.

Moreover, school heads' instructional leadership in terms of students' service and development program denotes negligible correlation to teachers' level of teaching performance as evident in the computed *rs* value of .002 which is lower than the *p*-value of .986. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. It can be argued understandably that teachers' level of teaching performance is not predictive of students' services and development program which means that school heads' instructional leadership functions in terms of providing students' services in school and other development activities were not factors that stimulated teachers' teaching performance and competence.

These findings were contradictory and differing from to the findings of Archibong (2022), Afandi (2023), and Cockpim and Somprach (2021) who judiciously conveyed, reported, and found out based on their studies that administration and supervision of instructional activities and programs; human resource development programs; and, students' services and development programs of the school heads in the Philippines schools influenced teachers' level of teaching performance and effectiveness.

It can be inferred based on findings that teachers' level of teaching performance is attributed to other factors or variables not included in this study such as trainings and seminars and conferences on teaching-learning strategies and methodologies, number of years of comprehensive teaching experience, personal and professional commitment and dedication to the teaching profession, and the rigid pre-teachers education trainings from universities and colleges.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

School heads' administrative performance and instructional leadership practices are factors that influenced teachers' teaching performance and effectiveness because they stimulate performance. However, there are factors that may describe teachers' teaching performance such as the rigid pre-teachers trainings in colleges and universities where they obtained their education degrees, practical trainings or conferences and seminars workshops attended on teaching-learning methodologies and strategies, productive years of teaching in the public elementary schools, and teachers' personal dedication and commitment to the teaching profession are factors and variables that arguably and defensively define and describe teachers' level of teaching performance.

Teachers' teaching performance is not predictive of the school heads' administrative performance and instructional leadership practices. Hence, it is recommended to the Schools Division Superintendent, District Supervisor, and the School Heads in the public elementary school shall implement the following developmental program for teachers in order to sustain the teachers' teaching performance on the following trainings; Safeguarding Education: Education Continuity Planning and the Whole-School Approach; Innovation in Education; Classroom Management: Uncovering Deeper Layers of Learning and Supporting Students with Learning Disabilities; and,

demofest on educational innovation, technology and leadership.

References

- Almonia, R. 2001. "Leadership Behavior of Elementary and Secondary School Administrators in the Division of Camiguin". Unpublished Master's Thesis, BSC, Malaybalay, Bukidnon.
- Aquino, G. 1985. Educational Management. Principles, Functions and Concepts. Manila, Philippines: Rex Book Store, Company.
- Awa, D. 2003. "Task and Performance Management of School Administrators of Non-sectarian Private Schools in the Province of Bukidnon". Unpublished Master's Thesis, Bukidnon State College.
- Bar-on, H. 2006. Working with Administrative Competence: Drive to Managerial Performance. New York: Consulting Psychologist Press.
- Bennet, T. 2003. Leadership. New York: Prentice Hall, Inc.
- Bercero, E. A. 2011. "Causal Model of Conflict Management Effectiveness of School Administrators of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the Province of Bukidnon". Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation, Doctor of Management, Capitol University, Cagayan de Oro City, Philippines.
- Blanchard, K., et al. 2005. Leadership and the One Minute Manager: Increasing Effectiveness Through Situation Leadership. New York: William Marrow and Co., Inc.
- Boado, I. 2003. "Administrative and Supervisory Abilities and Qualities of Deans in Private Colleges and Universities in Dagupan City and Northern Luzon". Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation, Lyceum of the City of Baguio.
- Bourn, J. 2006. Management in Central Local Government: Government and Administration Series. London: Pitman Publishing Limited.
- Bradberry, A. 2005. Administrative Performance at work. New York: Prentice Hall International, Inc.
- Cabanelez, T. 2005. "Communication Behavior and School Leadership Styles of Select School Administrators in the Province of Bukidnon". Unpublished Master's Thesis, Bukidnon State College, Malaybalay City, Philippines.
- Carson, S. 1993. "Some Measures of Participative Management as Related to Organizational Performance". Dissertation Abstract International, University of Arkansas.
- Caruso, D. 2002. The Management Competence Quick Book. New Jersey: Prentice Hall International, Inc.
- Chan, G. 2003. "Processes on Participative Leadership and Motivation in relation to Educational Management Effectiveness". Dissertation Abstract International. Pennsylvania State University.
- Dalima, S. 2004. "Faculty Development Program for Teaching Effectiveness of Seventh-Day Adventist Schools of General Santos City". Unpublished Master's Thesis. Notre Dame University of Marbel, South Cotabato.
- Davis, K. 2004. Human Behavior at Work: Organizational Behavior. USA: 6th Ed. McGraw Hill International Book.
- Dramayo, A. 2004. "Administrative Performance of Instructional Leaders of Select Schools in the Province of Surigao Del Sur". Unpublished Master's Thesis, Bukidnon State College, Malaybalay City, Philippines.
- Drucker, P. 1979. The Effective Executive. New York: Harper and Row Publishers, Inc.
- Drucker, P. 2005. Task, Responsibilities, and Practices. New York: Harper and Row Publishers, Inc.
- Espinas, D. 2009. "A Causal Model of Negotiation Competency of School Administrators in Bukidnon, Philippines". A Dissertation, Central Mindanao University, Musuan, Bukidnon, Philippines.
- Faiman, F. 2006. Group Leadership and Democracy. Boston: Houghton Mifflin Co.
- Fraenkel, J. et al. 1993. How to Design and Evaluate Research in Education. USA: McGraw-Hill, Inc.
- Fulmer, E. et al. 2007. Exploring New Management. 3rd Edition. A Study Guide with cases, Readings, Incidents, and Exercises. New Jersey: McMillan Publishing Co. Inc.
- Furnham, A. 2002. Administrative Performance Assessment. University College London: UCL Press.
- Gahum, E. 2010. "Instructional Leadership Effectiveness of School Administrators of the Seventh-Day Adventists Colleges in Mindanao". Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation, Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Administration. Central Mindanao University, Musuan, Bukidnon. Philippines.

- Garces, N. 2005. "Leadership Adaptability of Bukidnon Secondary Schools Administrators". Unpublished Master's Thesis, Bukidnon State College, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, Philippines.
- Genove, MC. (2017). Effective Instructional Leadership. Journal of Education. Silliman University. Published November, 2017.
- Goleman, D. 2005. Administrative Performance: Why It can Matter More Than I.Q. London: Oxford University Press.
- Goleman, D. 2006. Administrative Performance: Why It can Matter More Than I.Q. (Second International Edition). London: Oxford University Press.
- Gonzales, R. 2004. "Management Practices of Bukidnon Secondary Schools Administrators". Unpublished Master's Thesis, Bukidnon State College, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, Philippines.
- Greaves, S. 2005. Multi-Rater Assessment and Self-Management Assessment. New York: McGraw Hill.
- Guimary, L. 2003. "Administrative Practices of School Administrators of Select Districts in the Division of Bukidnon". Unpublished Master's Thesis. Bukidnon State College, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, Philippines.
- Guria, M. 2004. "Person-Oriented School Management in Eliciting Desirable Work Performance: Approaches and Processes". Unpublished Master's Thesis. Philippine Normal University.
- Holt, D. 2007. Management Principles and Practices. Eaglewood Cliffs, New Jersey: Prentice Hall, Inc.
- House, R. 1991. Management Theory. The Wharton School. University of Pennsylvania. Philadelphia: University Press.
- Jafee, J., et al. 2005. The Art of Managing: How to Access and Perfect Your Management Style. Massachusetts: Adison-Wesley Publishing Co. Inc.
- Kaufman, H. 2006. Administrative Decentralization in Current Issues of Publication. New York: Hill St. Martin's Press.
- Koontz, H., et al. 1989. Principles of Management: An Analysis of Managerial Functions. New York: McGraw Hill.
- Landy, L. 2005. Trait-based Administrative Competence Self-Efficacy. New York: Cornell University Press.
- Martires, M. 2005. Introduction to Management. Massachusetts: Adison-Wesley Publishing Co. Inc.
- Mayer, J. 2001. Systematic Theoretical Accounts of Emotional Competence. International Edition. USA: McGraw Hill Book Co.
- Mayer, C. 2001. Organizational Performance Effectiveness. Boston, Massachusetts: Kent Publishing Company. A Division of Wodsworth, Inc.
- McAlpine, T. 2004. The Process of Management: Major Features of Management Performance. New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House, Pvt. Ltd.
- McFarland, M. 2006. Criticism of Theoretical Foundation of Administrative Competence. New York: Consulting Psychologist Press.
- Mercado, M. 2005. "Organizational Effectiveness of Instructional Leaders of Information Technology Schools in Northern Mindanao". Master's Thesis. University of Mindanao. Davao City.
- Milano, M. 2005. "Leadership Styles of Bukidnon Provincial Government Administrators". Unpublished Master's Thesis, Bukidnon State College, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, Philippines.
- Mukhi, S. 1981. "Relationship Between Leadership Styles, Climate and Performance of the Organization". Dissertation Abstract International, University of New South Wales, Australia.
- Nacer, A. 2005. "Instructional Leadership and Performance Effectiveness of Teachers and Academic Heads of St. Paul University System". Unpublished Master's Thesis. SPU.
- Namoc, E. 2006. "Administrative Organizational Performance of Department Heads of Service Units of the Provincial Government of Bukidnon". Unpublished Master's Thesis. Bukidnon State College, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, Philippines.
- Nang, N. 2004. "Leadership Accountability and Performance of School Administrators in Secondary Schools in Cebu City". Unpublished Master's Thesis. USJR
- Nigro, N., et al. 1989. Introduction to Public Administration. USA: McGraw-Hill Publishing Company, Inc.
- Okit, A. 2004. "Leadership Empowerment of Tertiary and Secondary School Teachers of Bukidnon". Unpublished Master's Thesis. Bukidnon State College, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, Philippines.
- Ornieta, S. (2004). Instructional Leadership and Accountability of Primary School Principals of Agusan Del Sur. Master's Thesis. Father Urios University.

- Ortiga, R. 2002. "Instructional Resources Management and Development Programs of Non-Sectarian Schools of General Santos City". Unpublished Master's Thesis, Notre Dame University of Marbel, South Cotabato.
- Paulhus, D., et al. 2006. *Meta-analyses of Administrative Competence*. International Edition. New York: Consulting Psychologist Press.
- Payne, S. 2006. *Administrative Performance Book*. International Publication. USA: McGraw Hill Book, Co.
- Petrides, K. 2002. *Administrative and Organizational Performance Global Assessment Test*. London: University of London Press.
- Plunkett, A. 2005. *Introduction to Management*. 5th edition, Boston, Massachusetts: Kent Publishing Company. A Division of Woodworth, Inc.
- Rafols, N. 2006. "Work Performance and Job Satisfaction of Local Chief Executives in the Province of Bukidnon". Unpublished Master's Thesis, Bukidnon State College, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, Philippines.
- Ravanara, R. 2005. "Performance Effectiveness of Private High School Principals of Northern Bukidnon". Unpublished Master's Thesis, Bukidnon State College, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, Philippines.
- Reid, S., et al. 2006. *Global Administrative Performance Assessment and Appraisal*. International Edition. USA: McGraw Hill Book, Co.
- Reuven, B. 2006. *Administrative Performance Inventory*. New York: Consulting Psychologist Press.
- Rey, E. 2006. "Professional Commitment and Job Performance of Instructional Leaders of BUACS Member Schools". Unpublished Master's Thesis. University of San Carlos, Cebu City, Philippines.
- Ruiz, R. 2007. "Assessment on Leadership and Performance Effectiveness of Teachers and School Administrators of Select Schools in the Province of Lanao del Sur". Unpublished Master's Thesis, Mindanao State University, Marawi City, Philippines.
- Salovey, P. 2002. *A Study on Administrative Performance: Developing Administrative Competence*. International Edition. USA: McGraw Hill Book, Co.
- Senar, J. 2003. "Instructional Performance and Satisfaction of Episcopal Diocese of Southern Philippines". Unpublished Master's Thesis. Central Mindanao University, Musuan, Bukidnon, Philippines.
- Stoner, J., et al. 2007. *Management*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall International Editions, 5th Edition.
- Stydell, R. 2003. *Fundamental of Management*. 6th edition, USA: McGraw Hill Publishing Company, Inc.
- Ullman, A. 1996. *Developing model parameters in linear relationships of variables*. 2nd edition, USA: McGraw Hill Publishing Company, Inc.
- Waltman, A. 2005. *Human Resource Management*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall International Edition. 3rd Edition.
- Wankel, D. 2003. *Organizational Communication*. 3rd edition, Kent Publishing Company. New York: McGraw Hill Book Co.

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